

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF THE SIGNALIZED
INTERSECTION OF TROY, GOSHEN, AND CENTER GROVE
ROADS USING MICROSCOPIC SIMULATION.

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Bachelor's In civil engineering

AUGUST 2024

A Research Paper Submitted in Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Master of Science Degree

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ABSTRACT

The study provides an overview of the current congestion at the signalized intersection of Troy Road, Center Grove Road and Goshen Road in Edwardsville, Illinois. Given its high traffic volume, especially during peak hours, a detailed analysis was necessary using VISSIM software to identify the optimal solution for reducing vehicle delay, stopped delay, and queue length. After the models were calibrated and validated, the performance was evaluated under the current traffic conditions. Firstly, the assessment focused on the existing state of the intersection, then for three models with modifications that resulted in significant improvement in the performance measures and Level of Service (LOS). Statistical analyses were performed to evaluate and compare the result of each scenario with the existing condition. Each scenario showed reduction in delay (vehicle delay and stop delay at the intersection), thereby enhancing intersection performance. Despite the most impactful scenario - adding the through lanes in the minor road (Centre Grove Road and the Goshen Road), factors such as cost, right of way (ROW), and construction time make it less viable. Based on the vehicle delay, LOS and stop delay, the traffic signal coordination scenario emerged as the best.

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1. Introduction

Traffic congestion has become a major concern for expanding cities like Edwardsville, Illinois. Traffic congestions occur when the demand exceeds the capacity of transportation infrastructure, resulting in longer travel time and delays. Rapid urbanization in emerging cities could generate traffic congestion, particularly impacting the daily lives of people by increasing mental stress and causing unexpected travel delays. Moreover, traffic congestion has a negative impact on the economy.

Intersections play an important role in managing conflict and merging traffic streams. Geometric and traffic studies were conducted at the selected intersections that were heavily affected, particularly during peak hours, to determine whether the overall vehicle delay and queues were operating well or exceeding capacity. The vehicle delay analysis and the stop vehicle delay are critical components of the study.

The research aimed to study the approaches and tools used in the analysis of intersecting signals, with a focus on their applications and consequences in various contexts. By simulating different traffic conditions and evaluating key performance indicators such as performance measure, travel times, and signal efficiency, this study aimed to provide the optimal and develop a sustainable transportation network capable of accommodating future growth while maintaining efficient and safe traffic flow.

2. Literature Review

A roadway intersection is an area where two or more roads join, and flow of traffic can make changes in the direction. The *Highway Capacity Manual (2022 HCM)* evaluates the effectiveness of a signalized intersection in several sections, including calculating saturation flow rate, Volume/Capacity (V/C), delay, and determining Level of Service (LOS). Average annual daily traffic serves as a basic parameter for travel demand forecasting and various traffic research. For a comprehensive study of an intersection and an actual representation of traffic, hourly flow rates would be utilized for traffic engineering study using HCM methodologies. The HCM described a method for assessing the performance of an intersection. The method focuses on the LOS for each type of facility that has analysis procedure available. Letters designate each level, from A to F, where “A” represents the best operation condition whereas “F” represents the worst. Each level represents range of average vehicle delay. Most design or planning efforts typically use service flow rates at LOS C or D to ensure the acceptable operating service for facility user, and each facility type has a defined method for assessing capacity level and LOS also has performance measures that can be calculated (Board et al. 2022).

2.1. Performance analysis of signalized intersection

Several studies focused on estimating the traffic condition and measuring the intersections performance. Marisamynathan et al. (2016) aimed to measure the performance levels of signalized intersections based on traffic and geometric characteristics. The study evaluated 12 hours of traffic data to analyze the performance of signalized intersection. Raw traffic data were analyzed, and V/C ratio was calculated (0.801) by using Indian Road Congress (IRC 106-1990) manual. Vehicle delay was calculated (39 sec) by using Webster’s formula and level of service (LOS) were determined. The performance evaluation showed the over saturation at Retteri junction, and

flyover was proposed to reduce the congestion level and huge vehicle delay (Marisamynathan and Lakshmi 2020).

Traffic flow at major intersections of an urban road has always been an entangled nonlinear process. In 2016, T.U. Chowdhury and Mohammad Raihan conducted a case study on a busy intersection in Dhaka, Bangladesh, aimed to reduce the traffic congestion. The intersection chosen was Banani-Kakoli, which connected three commercial zones (Mohakhali, Tongi and Gulshan) and one residential zone (Banani DOHS). The study identifies left and right turning movements as the main cause of the problems. To address the traffic congestion, the road capacity was increased (along the route or at bottlenecks, making new routes and betterment of traffic management). The study pointed out that the traffic congestion can be reduced by improving the roadway corridor as the intersections are an integrated element of the traffic system(Chowdhury et al. 2016).

Osuolale, O.M. (2019) evaluated the LOS at significant intersections in Ibadan, Nigeria, emphasizing the impact of traffic congestion on urban transportation. The field tests were conducted by researchers at the Mokola and Total Garden crossings, assessing traffic volume and delays between 7:00 a.m. and 7:00 p.m. on specific days. The statistics showed that passenger automobiles were the most prevalent, accounting for more than 40% of vehicles, with peak hours falling between 8 and 9 a.m. and 2 and 3 p.m. The average delay per vehicle ranged between 11.3 and 13.6 seconds, resulting in LOS B for all approaches, indicating acceptable congestion with minor capacity decreases(Osuolale et al. 2019).

Research conducted by Dukiya and Ajiboye (2011) examined the impact of urban road crossings at the Oga-Ikorodu "Y-junction" in Lagos, Nigeria. To measure intersection performance, the study used a variety of analytical approaches such as delay analysis, vehicle spot speed studies, and traffic volume surveys. The findings showed that the LOS at the crossroads fluctuated, with Ayangburen Road obtaining a morning LOS of B and Lagos and Sagamu roads

deteriorating to E during evening peaks. The frequent car stops, combined with pedestrian activity, road hawkers/peddlers(vendors), and illegal parking, increased traffic congestion. Recommendations to improve traffic flow included relocating the Ayangburen Market, revamping the crossroads for better traffic signaling, and establishing alternate routes to alleviate congestion(Dukiya and Ajiboye 2011).

2.2. Queue length estimation

In 2009, Liu proposed an innovative approach for estimating intersection queue lengths using existing detectors. Researchers had addressed the issue by introducing a new method that utilized high-resolution "event-based" traffic signal data and the Lighthill-Whitham-Richards (LWR) shockwave theory. Unlike existing methods, which were restricted by detector occupancy, their methodology utilized queue discharge patterns from previous cycles to accurately estimate current queue lengths. They emphasized the method's ability to distinguish between queue discharge and arrival traffic, which was crucial in congested settings where other strategies had failed. Evaluation against field data had shown satisfactory accuracy in estimating maximum queue lengths, although they acknowledged limitations such as arrival flow saturation and identification errors (Liu et al. 2009).

In 2015, Lee, Wong, and Li present an innovative method for real-time estimation of lane-based queue lengths based on isolated signalized junctions. To make the best use of detector data, they use discriminant models and Kalman filters together. The researchers determine the residual queues exist at the start of the cycle and estimate traffic volumes in each lane by using time occupancy rates and impulse memories from upstream and downstream detectors, respectively. The researcher aimed to study Lankershim Boulevard to demonstrate the method's robustness under a variety of traffic conditions, and the performance of a three-lane section at an isolated intersection was simulations with VISSIM. The study emphasizes the importance of calibrated

discriminant models and the Kalman filter in improving accuracy by reducing lane-changing complexity and errors in downstream arrival estimates(Lee et al. 2015).

2.3. "VISSIM"-Traffic Signals and coordination Study:

For Traffic modelling using the software tools designed for traffic simulation was an important supportive tool in decision-making and in choosing the optional solution. The research done by Fabianova (2019) aimed to introduce the application of VISSIM program, in the analysis and simulating a model of the existing signal controlled at a congested intersection. The traffic flow was modeled for current conditions, and two scenarios: the addition through lane and the addition of a through lane with updated traffic signal timing. Queue length was monitored as measure of intersection throughput. Both improvements resulted in a significant reduction in the number of vehicles waiting in the most congested areas. The first model reduced average line length by 75%, while the second model improved right-turn traffic and reduced vehicle lines in other directions(Fabianova et al. 2020).

In the Study by Alit Suthanaya and Sudiram in Denpasar City, Indonesia, they addressed the pervasive issue of traffic congestion. They used the VISSIM software to coordinate between the closely spaced upstream and downstream intersections. The study aimed to improve traffic flow and reduce delays, queue lengths, and stop delays. Overall, the results showed a significant improvement: there was an 18.5% reduction in queue length, a 21.41% decrease in delays, and 21.61% reduction in stop delays, indicating the improvement in the traffic performances. The researchers validated these results through t-test statistical analysis, confirming signification improvement in between the observed and the predicted traffic volumes. This research highlights the efficacy of signals coordination in mitigating congestion and improving traffic efficiency on urban roads(Suthanaya and Putra 2023)

Similarly, the study conducted by Bhattarai and Marsani aimed to improve the traffic flow and minimize delays and travel times on busy streets of the Ghanthaghar and Naya Thimi intersections, using the PTV VISSIM software described the time-based traffic signals coordination. Through the calibrating and simulating the signals coordination, the research identified significant improvement resulting in reduced delay and travel time. Specifically, the study observed an average delay reduction of 6.13 veh-hrs with optimized offsets and 5.41 veh-hrs with equally distributed offsets, alongside notable decreases in travel time along a critical segment. The findings highlight that signal coordination, without significant changes to signals timing or infrastructure, can substantially improve traffic efficiency (Bhattarai and Marsani 2015).

Overall, finding from these studies suggest that various methods and tools have been effective in analyzing and improving the performance of signalized intersections. Those methods have been applied in different locations and contexts, revealing that addressing traffic congestion often requires a combination of improving the overall congestion. The research consistently shows that these interventions can lead to significant reductions in vehicle delay, stop delay, queue lengths, and overall congestion, thereby improving the LOS at intersections.

3. Problem Statement and Objective of the Study

3.1. Problems Statement

The total number of motor vehicles travelling across Troy Road, Center Grove Road and Goshen Road was 20,500(major) and 12,500(minor), according to the *Average Annual Daily Traffic "AADT (IDOT)"*. The intersection experienced the traffic congestions, especially during peak hour (8-10 am and 4-6pm). This congestion was caused by the several factors, which also included busy commercial zone, connected with establishments such as Target, Sam's Club, UPS, Chick Fill-A, and a convenience store (Quick Trip). Over the years this has led to a significant

increase in the traffic volume which mainly connected in minor road as shown in [Figure 1](#). Although the signal timing functions differently according to the peak and normal hours, the intersection still faces traffic congestion.

3.2. Objectives of the Study

The primary goals of this study were to evaluate the performance of the intersection and to suggest strategies for the improving its efficiency. The study aimed to provide an existing status of traffic in a signalized intersection in terms of LOS and queue length. The performance results from the different alternatives will guide the recommendations.

4. Methodology

4.1. Background Study Area

For this research study, the study area selected was the Troy Rd. intersection located at 38.781399°N, -89.951371°E. The intersection was 4-legged operated by traffic signals, Troy Road was the primary road and the minor road had different names, Goshen Road and Center Grove Road, see [Figure 1](#). The traffic signals operate at the intersection as south leg towards IL 159, east leg toward Goshen Road, north leg was towards Troy Rd, and west leg towards Center Grove Rd respectively. All the left turn lanes were operated as protected/permitted. The major road had separate left turn lanes, through lanes and the shared lane (through + right turn), while the minor road had left turn and the shared lane (through + right turn). During the study, the existing conditions included a cycle length of 136 seconds. The minimum green time was 7 seconds for phases – 1,3,4,5,7,8 and 10 seconds for phases 2 and 6 as shown in [Table 1](#). The yellow 4 seconds time was set for all phase except phase 6, and the red clearance ranged from 2.4 to 3.1 seconds shown in [Table 1](#). The intersection was labeled with the different phase where phase 2 and 6 was the major phase see Figure 2, respectively.

Figure 1: Intersection of Troy Road, Goshen Road, and Center Grove Road

Table 1: Existing Traffic Timing Setting

Phase/Pattern	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Left Turn Type	Prot/Perm		Prot/Perm		Prot/Perm		Prot/Perm	
Min Green (Sec)	7	10	7	7	7	10	7	7
Veh Ext.	3	5.5	3.5	4	3	5.5	4	4
MAX 1 (Sec)	20	40	20	30	20	40	20	30
MAX 2	30	50	30	40	30	50	30	40
Yellow	4	4.1	4	4	4	4.7	4	4
Red Clearance	2.4	2.4	3.1	3.1	2.4	2.4	3.1	2.3

Figure 2: Phase and Ring Barrier Diagram

4.2. Data Collection

To perform an intersection analysis, it was necessary to gather data on geometric characteristics, traffic characteristics, and signal control characteristics. Most of the data relating to these categories was obtained through traffic surveys and field observations. The term of the traffic surveys and field observation was on intersection for an hour with 15-minute intervals, collected on 02/22/2024 (Thursday) using the Traffic Count app. The most congested period (Peak Hours) at the intersection was in the afternoon (16:30 to 17:30) on weekdays. The following data were collected:

- a) Intersection geometry, which includes lane type, lane traffic control, lane discipline, etc.
- b) Classified counts of vehicles during - Peak Hours period observations
- c) Current signal timing and phasing data
- d) Vehicles entering/exiting from adjacent land uses such as Quick Trip and the UPS Store.

Other data such as approach leg distances and lane widths, were obtained using the measure tool available in Google Maps. Saturation flow, vehicle class, vehicle dimensions, queue space & vehicle occupancy were assumed as secondary data. The data were collected for the period of one hour with every 15 min interval, see [Table 2](#). The primary issues observed during data collection were exacerbated by the presence of commercial business driveway nearby the intersection, so the entering/exiting data were collected as shown in [Table 3](#). Similarly, during the field observations, the minor road seems to be more congested with the traffic queue more than the major road, the max queue lengths of around 900 ft was noted. These queues occurred not only during peak hours but before too.

Table 2: Data Collection at the intersection

Times	North Bound			Total Veh.	South Bound			Total Veh.	West Bound			Total Veh.	East Bound			Total Veh.
	LT	TH	RT		RT	TH	LT		RT	TH	LT		LT	TH	RT	
4:30 to 4:45	19	172	29	220	17	183	27	227	29	72	42	143	45	91	14	150
4:45 to 5:00	23	197	38	258	20	203	32	255	27	69	43	139	38	99	12	149
5:00 to 5:15	32	190	35	257	21	174	34	229	31	63	39	133	52	96	17	165
5:15 to 5:30	18	172	55	245	14	144	37	195	36	81	46	163	41	68	19	128
Total Veh.	92	731	157	980	72	704	130	906	123	285	170	578	176	354	62	592
Ratio	0.09	0.7	0.2	1	0.1	0.8	0.14	1	0.21	0.49	0.29	1	0.29	0.6	0.1	1

Table 3: QT and UPS data Collection

Times	Vehicles Enter	
	Qt	UPS
4:30 to 4:45	15	10
4:45 to 5:00	19	16
5:00 to 5:15	16	14
5:15 to 5:30	11	9
Total Veh.	74	61

4.3. Type of Road Users and Priority Consideration

At this location, the traffic consisted of passenger cars, transit vehicles, trucks, school buses, and emergency vehicles. The intersection did not have a pedestrian crosswalk, so the research did not include pedestrian effects.

5. Intersection Modelling and Scenarios

5.1. VISSIM Model

The VISSIM model was constructed by tracing the roadway network over the aerial photograph provided in the background of the software. The number of lanes, location of lane additions and drops, and other geometry details were confirmed through the field visit. Based on the data obtained from the traffic survey, the road intersection characteristics were defined including all the necessary traffic signals components, signal timing, traffic, and speed limits.

The simulation duration was set to be 1 hour and 15 minutes, with the first 15 minutes as warm-up time. The total number of runs was set as 10 and an average output of 10 runs was considered as the VISSIM output. In total, four VISSIM models were created, the first model used existing data to verify the real-world simulation. The intersection geometry, number of lanes, and the exact vehicle data were also included to match the actual location.

For the VISSIM calibration, the Origin/Destination matrix data was used see Table 4. A total of 6 zones were to describe the flow of traffic, as shown in Figure 3. Overall, 26 routes were assigned with vehicle input, see Figure 4. Figure 5 shows Troy Road’s network in PTV VISSIM 2023. After finalizing the existing scenario, three alternatives’ scenarios were introduced: adding right turn lane, adding new through lanes and the coordinating with upstream and downstream signals intersection.

Table 4: Origin/Destination data

O/D	1	2	3	4	5	6	Total
1	0	171	0	57	133	79	440
2	177	0	0	54	125	74	430
3	0	0	0	12	27	17	56
4	50	68	12	0	72	704	906
5	137	186	31	172	0	62	588
6	61	82	14	731	92	0	980

Figure 3: Origin/Destination Zones

Start Page Network Editor

Static Vehicle Routing Decisions / Static vehicle routes

Static vehicle routes

Cou...	No	Na	Link	Pos	AllVehTypes	VehCl...	RouteChoice	Count: 26	V...	No	IfDestLink	DestPos	RelFlow(0-MAX)
1	1	2		1.219	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Static	1	1	1	4: EB	274.336	0.388
2	2	5: WBTH		0.819	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Static	2	1	2	12: NB-TROY FOLLOW	1328.882	0.132
3	3	23: Target		2.560	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Static	3	1	3	17: WB-GROVE FOLLO...	1461.835	0.300
4	4	14: SB- TROY		3.685	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Static	4	1	5	13: TROY SB FOLLOW	991.902	0.180
5	5	15: EB GRO...		0.801	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Static	5	2	1	8: SB	299.748	0.410
6	6	21: NB 159		4.069	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Static	6	2	2	12: NB-TROY FOLLOW	1333.278	0.130
								7	2	3	17: WB-GROVE FOLLO...	1462.011	0.290
								8	2	5	13: TROY SB FOLLOW	988.955	0.170
								9	3	1	12: NB-TROY FOLLOW	1332.853	0.210
								10	3	2	17: WB-GROVE FOLLO...	1458.269	0.480
								11	3	4	13: TROY SB FOLLOW	989.332	0.310
								12	4	2	8: SB	297.623	0.060
								13	4	3	4: EB	274.167	0.075
								14	4	4	10	83.675	0.013
								15	4	5	17: WB-GROVE FOLLO...	1460.164	0.080
								16	4	6	13: TROY SB FOLLOW	989.787	0.772
								17	5	1	8: SB	292.411	0.230
								18	5	2	4: EB	270.080	0.320
								19	5	3	10	81.716	0.050
								20	5	4	12: NB-TROY FOLLOW	1332.728	0.300
								21	5	5	13: TROY SB FOLLOW	985.060	0.100
								22	6	1	8: SB	301.036	0.062
								23	6	2	4: EB	275.438	0.082
								24	6	3	10	85.475	0.015
								25	6	4	12: NB-TROY FOLLOW	1334.127	0.745
								26	6	5	17: WB-GROVE FOLLO...	1464.992	0.096

Figure 4: Vehicle input with O/D route

Figure 5: Modelling in VISSIM

5.2. Traffic Signal Controller:

After the addition of lanes and vehicle data to the simulation, a traffic signals time model was created based on the data obtained from the Traffic Signal Control Cabinets (NEMA), as shown in [Table 1](#). Similarly, the signal control on intersection was assigned with the Phase and Ring Barrier signal controller, see [Figure 2](#). A total of 10 detectors were added in the intersection, each associated with a phase. For realistic signal operations, an 8-phase ring sequence was operated with the same signal timing as the existing system, see [Figure 6](#).

Figure 6: Traffic Signal Controller

5.3. Traffic Signal Coordination:

Ensuring safe and efficiently movements at intersections was one of the key goals of traffic signals timing setting. Achieving a perfect and reasonable coordination plan was impossible without recognizing the factors affecting signal coordination. Traffic signal coordination plans were strongly influenced by parameters such as corridor speeds, signal spacing, traffic volumes, traffic congestion, cycle lengths, phasing sequences, offsets. In this model- Cycle length, phase split, offset, and platoon were considered.

5.4. Calibration and Validation of Model

5.5.2. Calibration:

The objectives of model calibration were to obtain the best match possible between the field and the model performance in software. The number of vehicles were compared between the simulated and observed. There was no volume different more than 6% and the overall volume was within 5%, not exceed 10% of the count traffic volume ([MDOT](#)). For instance, the total number of vehicles from Zone 4 during observed was 906, while during the calibration the node counted the number of 936, i.e. 4%. After confirming the vehicle flow was accurate and the traffic signals were operating correct, the driver behavior parameters were considered. The average distance of 4 feet standstill was used based on the previous research in this area(Fries et al. 2018). [Figure 7](#). displays the average vehicle count obtained from comparing the observed vehicle count with the VISSIM.

Figure 7: Observation vs VISSIM model data for Calibration

5.5.2. Validation:

Validation determines whether the selected model is appropriate for the given condition and for the given task (HCM). So, to validate the queue length and the vehicle count, the

average queue in the VISSIM model at the time the red signals was compared to the real queue and the total number of vehicles count for the one-hour period, that was seen during data collection. This stage contributed to the simulation's maximum realism being confirmed. Face validation confirmed the queue lengths predicted in VISSIM matched the real-world observations and the model was considered calibrated and validated.

6. Design and Verification of new Intersection Models:

Overall, the problems of congestion at the intersection were addressed in three ways in the following simulation models:

- ✓ In the first model, a separate right lane was added for the major and the minor roads, it will allow right turn on read and to be controlled by the traffic signal.
- ✓ In the second model, a new through lane was added to the minor road.
- ✓ In the third model, coordination was used between the major road upstream and downstream traffic signals.

6.1. Adding the Right Turn Lane

The researcher observed significant congestion along the minor and major lane due to limited queuing space. To address the issue of queue length and congestion, the first scenario, adding a right turn lane, was simulated. During the field observation, the queue lengths on Centre Grove Rd. and Goshen Rd. exceeded 500 meters, similarly a bit less in the Troy Road. Although the right turn vehicles were fewer as compared to the through lane, these movement share a lane and interact. To overcome this problem, a right turn lane was added in all directions to analyze the performance of the intersection.

6.2. Addition of a Through Lane minor (Centre Grove Rd & Goshen Road)

Another scenario to improve the intersection affects both Eastbound as well as the Westbound. According to the site, the smaller route had the most difficulty, even with less volume than the major road due to lane issues. A new through lane was added to both eastbound as well as westbound approaches, and a share through-right lane was kept.

6.3. Coordination:

Out of all the scenarios, this one does not require additional pavement area. According to the *Traffic Signal Timing Manual (2021)*, coordination was primarily a deliberate method to synchronizing multiple intersections to enhance the operation of one or more directional movements in a system. In the model, coordination was done with the upstream and downstream intersection with the major intersection. The cycle length was 136 seconds, and the main intersection phases 2 and 6 was coordinate to the follow up and downstream with respect to both distance and vehicle volume. Coordination decisions were made by the Coupling Index value which was more than 1 and distance smaller than 2500. Similarly, the offset value was determined with respect to the distance (1090ft and 1490ft) and the speed (45mph), the 111 seconds for Northbound and 108 seconds for Southbound respectively as shown in [Figure 8](#). and [9](#).

Figure 8: Northbound Coordination

Figure 9: Southbound Coordination

7. Results:

7.1. Measure of Effectiveness

7.1.1 Vehicle Delay

Vehicle delay was described in seconds per vehicle and was a comparison between flowing freely through the intersection and traveling through the intersection with other vehicles. During the simulation, a Node was set to collect multiple data by running the model for ten times and taking the average. [Table 5](#). displayed the vehicle delay for the existing scenario and all three proposed scenarios. The existing scenario had an average delay of 52.2 seconds and variance of 57.5 seconds. The scenarios demonstrated a reduction in both average delay and variance, which demonstrate the significant improvement and reduction of traffic congestion at the intersection.

Table 5: Vehicle Delay

	EXISTING	1 ST SCENARIO	2 ND SCENARIO	3 RD SCENARIO
Average Delay (sec)	52.22	41.42	37.27	41.59
Variance (sec ²)	57.63	5.66	2.21	38.58

7.1.2 Vehicle Stop Delay:

In VISSIM, “Vehicle stops” simply meant when the vehicles stopped at the intersections during the simulation. These stops provided the guidance on traffic flow and signals timing setting i.e., minimum, or maximum green time for the intersections where vehicle passed the intersection on their first green signal. The result for the first and second, scenarios suggest that - the node delay with vehicle stops don’t significantly changed as much as compared to the third scenario. Vehicle Stop delay for the existing and all three scenarios were displayed in [Table 6](#). In the scenario three, the coordination scenario, adjustments in signal timing for coordination with upstream and downstream intersection resulted in less stop as compared to the existing. this indicates that the coordination effectively reduces the stop time and queue at the intersections.

Table 6: Vehicle Stop Delay

	EXISTING	1 st SCENARIO	2 nd SCENARIO	3 rd SCENARIO
Average Stop Delay (sec)	0.8443	0.812	0.811	0.683
Variance (sec ²)	0.0016	0.0013	0.0014	0.0036

7.1.3 Queue Delay:

There was a significant improvement in both major and minor queue delays. While simulated with all scenarios, the queue delays showed the significant improvement as compared to the existing. Specifically, in the second scenario, queue delays were improved significantly, whereas in the first and third scenarios, there was not so much significant improvement in queue delays. Regarding the coordination scenario, there was statistical significance improvement in queue delays at data collection points 3 and 4, but not at points 1 and 2, see [Figure 10](#). Overall, the scenario that yields the best results for queue delays was when the E-W through lane (i.e., at the minor road) was added.

Figure 10: Queue Length

7.2. T statistics:

To prove that there were significant changes in the vehicle delay and stops delay, statistical analysis was done using a t-Test. Paired t-Test are commonly used to test means of a sample before and after some treatment, i.e., two sample of data before and after an adding change. The test determines whether the means of a sample was significantly different from the specified value. For the t-test, one test and two tests are performed with the t value for each scenario along with a 95% confidence interval. In this t-Test, the test showed the P-value($T \leq t$) less than alpha (0.05), therefore can reject the null hypothesis that there was a statistically significant difference in the means of each variance. In this research, vehicle delay and stop delay within the node were used for the performance analysis, as they only focused on the intersection. [Table 7](#) and [8](#) shows the t-Test results with the constant existing variance throughout the different scenarios with vehicle delays and stop delay.

Table 7: t-Test Vehicle Delay

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means	<i>Existing</i>	<i>1st Scenario</i>	<i>2nd Scenario</i>	<i>3rd Scenario</i>
Mean	52.22	41.42	37.27	41.59
Variance	57.63	5.66	2.21	38.58
Observations	10	10	10	10
Pearson Correlation		0.75	0.39	0.68
Hypothesized Mean Difference		0	0	0
df		9	9	9
t Stat		5.66	6.62	5.92
P(T<=t) one-tail		0.00015	0.00005	0.00011
t Critical one-tail		1.83	1.83	1.83
P(T<=t) two-tail		0.00031	0.00010	0.00022
t Critical two-tail		2.26	2.26	2.26

Table 8: t-Test Stop Vehicle Delay

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means	<i>Existing</i>	<i>1st Scenario</i>	<i>2nd Scenario</i>	<i>3rd Scenario</i>
Mean	0.843	0.812	0.811	0.683
Variance	0.0016	0.0013	0.0014	0.0036
Observations	10	10	10	10.00000
Pearson Correlation		0.19	0.46	0.22
Hypothesized Mean Difference		0	0	0
df		9	9	9
t Stat		2.03	2.53	7.91
P(T<=t) one-tail		0.037	0.016	0.00001
t Critical one-tail		1.83	1.83	1.8331
P(T<=t) two-tail		0.073	0.032	0.00002
t Critical two-tail		2.26	2.26	2.26

8. Summary and Conclusion

The focus of this study was to identify ways to improve the existing condition of stop delays, queue length, vehicle delay, and congestion at the intersection of Troy Road, Centre Grove Road, and Goshen Road. Three scenarios were simulated: adding right turn lane, adding through lane and coordination using the PTV VISSIM software. The analysis indicated that adding through lane through analysis on vehicle delay, stop delay and LOS was best performance among the scenarios. The statistical analysis showed significant reductions in vehicle delay and vehicle stop delay at a significantly level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

The current analysis of the intersection was based on 6 O/D and did not fully consider the impact from all driveways of nearby businesses on traffic volume at intersection. So, to enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of future research, it was recommended to conduct the network for the analysis.

For the recommendation, the study taken through different sector. While adding through lanes showed the best result among the scenarios, the factors like cost, right of way, and construction time were noted which limits its feasibility among other. On comparing with overall vehicle delay, stop delay, right of way and construction time, coordination results as the best preferred scenario for this intersection.

References

- Bhattarai, B., and Marsani, A. (2015). *Time Based Traffic Signal Coordination (A Case Study of Gatthaghar and Naya Thimi Intersections)*.
- Board, T. R., National Academies of Sciences, E., and Medicine (2022). *Highway Capacity Manual 7th Edition: A Guide for Multimodal Mobility Analysis*, The National Academies Press, Washington, DC.
- Chowdhury, T., Raihan, S. M., Fahim, A., and Bhuiyan, M. A. "A case study on reduction of traffic congestion of Dhaka City: Banani Intersection." *Proc., International Conference on Agricultural, Civil and Environmental Engineering (ACEE-16)*, 61-65.
- Dukiya, J., and Ajiboye, A. (2011). *Performance analysis of urban road intersections and its environmental implication: a case study of the Lagos metropolitan area*.
- Fabianova, J., Michalik, P., Janekova, J., and Fabian, M. (2020). "Design and evaluation of a new intersection model to minimize congestions using VISSIM software." *Open Engineering*, 10, 48-56.
- Lee, S., Wong, S. C., and Li, Y. C. (2015). "Real-time estimation of lane-based queue lengths at isolated signalized junctions." *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 56, 1-17.
- Liu, H. X., Wu, X., Ma, W., and Hu, H. (2009). "Real-time queue length estimation for congested signalized intersections." *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 17(4), 412-427.
- Marisamynathan, S., and Lakshmi, S. (2020). "Performance Analysis of Signalized Intersection at Metropolitan Area." *Journal of Advanced Research in Applied Sciences and Engineering Technology*, 2(1), 19-29.
- Osolale, O., Durodola, T., and Soladoye, E. (2019). "Evaluation of Level of Service of Traffic at Major Road Intersections in Ibadan, Nigeria." *Evaluation*, 9(7).
- Suthanaya, P., and Putra, R. (2023). "Traffic Signal Coordination Based on Vissim Software (Case Study of Sudirman Road in Denpasar City, Indonesia)." *E3S Web of Conferences*, 445.
- Fries, R. N., Ghale, K., Dirks, B., & Qi, Y. (2018). Lessons learned from modeling the evacuation of a suburban university campus. International Conference on Transportation and Development 2018. [doi:10.1061/9780784481561.007](https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784481561.007)
- T-test: Paired two sample for Means. solver. (2024, January 2). <https://www.solver.com/t-test-paired-two-sample-means>
- ArcGIS Web Application, Annual Average Daily Traffic, 2024, "AADT IDOT" <https://www.gettingaroundillinois.com/Traffic%20Counts/index.html>

Appendix

A. Design and Verification of new Intersection Models:

1. Adding Right Turn Lanes

2. Adding Through Lanes

3. Coordination

B. Vehicle Delay:

1. Existing Vs Scenario First (Adding Right Turn)

2. Existing VS Scenario Second (Adding Through Lane)

3. Existing VS Scenario Third (Coordination)

C. Stop Delay:

1. Existing Vs Scenario First (Adding Right Turn)

2. Existing Vs Scenario Second (Adding Through Lane)

3. Existing Vs Scenario Third (Coordination)

Comparison of Intersection Performance